

Momentum and Space Entropies in the Bound State Schrodinger Equation

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In general, wavefunction $W(x)$ solutions of bound state quantum problems are obtained by solving a time-independent spatial differential Schrodinger equation. Traditionally, entropy or thermodynamic ideas do not enter as there is no temperature in the problem. Nevertheless, with Shannon's definition of entropy, even a $T=0$ bound state solution has probabilities $P(p)=f_p \cdot f_p$, $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p \text{ and } x)= P(p/x)P(x)= f_p \sin(px) W(x)$. As a result, one may calculate at least three Shannon's entropies for $T=0$ bound state solutions, namely S_p , S_x and $S(x \text{ and } p)$. S_p and S_x are not independent because $W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \ f_p \sin(px)$. Finding entropies may appear as simply a calculational exercise at this point. For the ground state of the quantum oscillator, however, $E= \text{Sum over } p \ S_p + \text{Integral } dx \ S_x$, so these entropies take the place of kinetic and potential energy terms. Furthermore, for the same problem, $\exp(-bp \cdot p)$ is of the form of an S_p maximized entropy, in the same manner as in classical statistical mechanics. Such an entropy maximization does not seem to hold for other cases. It is suggested, however, in this note that one might be able to generalize the ground state oscillator state result: $E= \text{Sum over } p \ S_p + \text{Integral } dx \ S_x$ to thermodynamic relations. Consider changing the oscillator spring constant infinitesimally. Then E , f_p , $W(x)$, S_p and S_x will all change in a tiny way. In such a case, one might consider:

$$dE = \text{Constant } d \{ \text{Sum over } p \ S_p + \text{Integral } dx \ S_x \}.$$

One might argue that changing the spring constant represents changing an external parameter which should be related to dW , a change in work. For the ground state harmonic oscillator, however, $d(V d(x))= (dV)d(x) + V(d/dx d(x))$ with $V(x)=\text{potential}$ and $d(x)=W(x)W(x)$, leads to the two terms $(dV)d(x)$ and $V(d/dx d(x))$ being proportional, so it is as if the change in work disappears from the problem. In this note, we suggest that for other cases, one may perhaps define an overall entropy $S=\text{Sum over } p \ S_p + \text{Integral } dx \ S_x$. Then, one could use the thermodynamic result:

$$dE - \text{Constant } dS = -dW$$

to calculate dW , an infinitesimal amount of work done. Such a recipe could perhaps be applied to closely spaced eigenstates for which one knows $E(n+1)$ and $E(n)$. The spatial entropies S_x are readily obtained from the wavefunctions $W_{n+1}(x)$ and $W_n(x)$ and the momentum entropies from the Fourier transforms inserted in Shannon's entropy equation. If such a procedure has meaning, it would show thermodynamics exists in quantum mechanics, even for $T=0$. It would also perhaps shed light on some $T>0$ Schrodinger type equations that are currently being presented in the literature as $\text{Sum over } p \ S_p + \text{integral } dx \ S_x$ is already being used as entropy.

Motivation

Traditionally, wavefunctions $W_n(x)$ have been obtained by solving the time-independent Schrodinger equation, with no particular focus on statistical mechanics. At a later stage, it was suggested statistical techniques could be added by assuming that added energy could cause

particles to jump between different states. This leads to the various Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein statistical approaches. Recently, however, there have been a number of papers in the literature (1), (2), (3) which have considered a modified Schrodinger equation, modified by including a wavefunction and temperature dependent potential. For $T=0$, the idea of a spatial Shannon's entropy $-2W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)]$ is proposed. Thus, the idea of spatial entropy is considered for the case of a $T=0$ bound state, even though it is not necessary for the solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equations.

From a statistical point of view, it seems the idea of entropy could apply to $T=0$ bound states. First of all, there is a spatial probability so:

$$S_x \text{ density} = - 2 W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)] \quad ((1))$$

seems to have some meaning. Secondly, for any quantum bound state:

$$\text{Kinetic energy} = \text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \quad f_p \quad ((2))$$

There are no spatial parts in this equation and it looks exactly like a classical statistical mechanics result. Thus, a momentum entropy also seems to be called for, namely:

$$S_p \text{ density} = - 2 f_p \ln[f_p] \quad ((3))$$

In quantum mechanical bound states, one seems to deal with conditional probabilities such as:

$$f_p \sin(px) / W(x) \quad \text{which appears in: } \text{KE at point } x = [\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m \quad f_p \sin(px)] / W(x) \quad ((4))$$

Note that in ((4)), f_p and not f_p^2 is used. Thus,

$$P(p/x)P(x) = P(x \text{ and } p) = W(x) f_p \sin(px) \quad (\text{or } \cos(px) \text{ depending on symmetry}) \quad ((5))$$

and this could be entered in Shannon's entropy equation. The problem is that taking the \ln of ((5)) leads to $\ln(|\sin(px)|)$ terms which make calculations a little problematic, although these can be solved by integration by parts. Actually, such terms appear in spatial entropy calculations of a particle in a box with no potential. It is interesting to note that Shannon's entropy using ((5)) summed over p and integrated over x gives rise to terms of the form:

$$\text{Sum over } p \quad S_p, \quad \text{Integral } dx \quad S_x \text{ and } \text{integral } dx \quad \sin(kx) f_p \sin(px) \ln[f_p \sin(px)], \quad ((5.5))$$

The third term being similar to the an entropy term appearing in a particle in a box.

Ground State Oscillator

The quantum ground state oscillator solution is interesting because $f_p = \exp(-bp^2)$ and $W(x) = \exp(-ax^2)$. In quantum mechanics, f_p and $W(x)$ are always related through a Fourier transform. For this special case, however, $W(x)W(x)$ and f_p^2 , match the classical statistical mechanical results for an oscillator. For the classical statistical mechanical case, one maximizes momentum entropy to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$. To add spatial dependence in the case of a potential $V(x)$, one notes that $p^2/2m + V(x) = E = \text{constant}$, so the distribution is really $\exp[-p^2/2m + V(x)/T]$. This result really seems to follow from the maximization of momentum space entropy alone. Thus, a similar "picture" seems to hold for the quantum oscillator ground state, although it seems that this is the case because various terms become equivalent and make it appear as if one has a free momentum gas at maximum entropy whose Fourier transform then leads to $\exp(-ax^2)$. (Actually, it seems that matters are more complicated, but at least this allows one to see quantum mechanics "appearing" as a classical statistical mechanical problem for this special case.

For the special case of the quantum oscillator ground state

$$F = \text{kinetic energy} - TS_p = 0. \quad ((6)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$E = \sum_p S_p + \int dx S_x \quad ((7))$$

where S_p and S_x are given by Shannon's entropy $-2f_p^2 \ln(f_p)$ and $-2W(x)W(x) \ln(W(x))$.

One may argue that ((7)) is simply a coincidence. In this note, however, we consider the possibility that:

$$S = \sum_p S_p + \int dx S_x \quad ((8))$$

may have some physical meaning for all quantum mechanical bound states.

It should be noted at this point that $S = -P(x \text{ and } p) \ln[P(x \text{ and } p)]$ gives a result similar to ((8)), but with an added term related to $\sin(kx) \sin(px) \ln[\sin(px)]$. Such a term is a little complicated to calculate (integration by parts is needed), but it seems to be related to the entropy of a particle in a box with no potential. For simplicity, we consider ((8)) in this note, but perhaps using $S = -P(x \text{ and } p) \ln[P(x \text{ and } p)]$ might be important for cases other than the oscillator.

Certainly ((7)) does not hold, nor will maximizing entropy (either S_p or S_x) lead to meaningful results. Even maximizing $S_p + S_x$ by changing f_p leads to somewhat complicated results.

It is suggested, however, that ((8)) may find meaning in at least two situations.

First, consider the case of a parametrized potential $V(b,x)$ where b is the parameter. The quantum oscillator potential is such an example, where the parameter is the spring constant. Changing b to $b+db$ will change $E(b)$ and $f_p(b)$. Thus, one can calculate dE and dS defined by ((8)) and take the difference. This may then yield a dW or infinitesimal work.

Secondly, consider the case where E_{n+1} and E_n are closely spaced which occurs when n becomes large. (Note: apparently $n=300$ has been reached for electron states in atoms.) Then: dE is approximately equal to $E_{n+1} - E_n$. One can similarly calculate entropy from ((8)) using $W_{n+1}(x)$ and $W_n(x)$ and the Fourier transforms $f_{n+1}(p)$ and $f_n(p)$. Taking the difference of dE and dS might yield work done.

Application to Particle in a Box

Let us try to apply $dE - C_1 dS = -dW$ using ((8)) to the case of a particle in a box with no potential. Here C_1 is a constant and:

$$W_n(x) = C (L/n) \sin(6.28nx/L)$$

$$dE = \text{constant} ((n+1)(n+1) - n^2) \approx \text{constant} (2n) / (L^2) \quad ((10))$$

For entropy from ((8)) one has:

$$S_x(n) = \int dx \ 2 C^2 (L^2/n^2) \sin^2(6.28nx/L) \ln[C \sqrt{L/n} \sin(6.28nx/L)] \quad ((11))$$

One needs to evaluate $S_x(n+1) - S_x(n)$. In general, integrals using $\sin^2(x) \ln(\sin(x))$ are solved by integration by parts. Here we are just wish to see if a "n" dependence is present.

It seems that:

$$S_x(n+1) - S_x(n) \text{ is proportional to } 1/(n+1)^2 - 1/n^2 \text{ or to } n^{-3}$$

For S_p , we note that a sine wave has $1/2i$ and $-1/2i$ as the factors regardless of n , $S_p(n+1)$ and $S_p(n)$ cancel in the case of a particle in a well without a potential. This will not normally be the case.

Thus, $S_x(n+1) + S_p(n+1) - [S_x(n) + S_p(n)]$ is of the order of n^{-3} , just like $E_{n+1} - E_n$.

According to the recipe suggested in this note, this means that work of the order of n^{-3} was done in moving the particle from the state n to the state $n+1$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in this note, we have tried to consider the idea of momentum entropy and spatial entropy given by Shannon's formula $-2f_p f_p \ln(f_p) + -2W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)]$ respectively.

We have also noted that a Shannon's entropy given by $-P(x \text{ and } p) \ln[P(x \text{ and } p)]$ may be more general. It yields S_p and S_x terms as well as single particle $\sin(px)$ entropy terms, but is more difficult to calculate.

For the case of the ground state oscillator we see that:

$$E = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } S_p + \text{Integral } dx \text{ } S_x$$

Thus, $dE = C d(S_p+S_x)$ for the ground state oscillator. If one changes the spring constant in order to bring about dE , it is suggested that work will be done, but it is proportional to changes in density so it as if no work is done, i.e. $dE = C d(S_p+S_x)$. In general, however, there will be work. In this note, we suggest that $dE - C d(S_p+S_x)$ may represent this infinitesimal work and apply this idea to "changing parameters" and closely spaced energy levels. The idea of an overall entropy which is $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } S_p + \text{Integral } dx \text{ } S_x$ may also apply to theories being developed for temperature dependent Schrodinger equations. These usually ascribe only a spatial entropy S_x to the $T=0$ state i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation. We seem to suggest that a sum of momentum and spatial entropies is already important at this stage, suggesting that these two may be important for $T>0$.

References

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